

An evaluation of SMAP soil moisture product using in situ data and Google Earth Engine: a case study from Greece

Spyridon E. Detsikas*, Triantafyllia Petsini, George P. Petropoulos

¹Department of Geography, Harokopio University of Athens, El. Venizelou 70, Kallithea, 17671, Athens, Greece

*Corresponding author: sdetsikas@hua.gr

Abstract

Obtaining Soil Moisture Content (SMC) over large scales is of key importance in several environmental and agricultural applications especially in the context of climate change and transition to digital farming. Remote sensing (RS) has a demonstrated capability in retrieving SMC over large areas with several operational products already available at different spatiotemporal resolution but with varying accuracy. The present study evaluates the performance of NASA's Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) 9 km product retrieved from the cloud platform Google Earth Engine (GEE) using in situ soil moisture data in a typical Mediterranean arid/semi-arid region located in central Greece for all year of 2020. The methodological workflow adopted includes standardized validation procedures employing a series of statistical measures to quantify the agreement between RS-based soil moisture product and the ground truth data. Our findings provide valuable insights into the capability of SMAP soil moisture data at retrieving more accurate SMC estimates at arid and semi-arid environments such as those found in the Mediterranean basin, while supporting also ongoing global validation efforts.

Keywords: *SMAP; Soil Moisture; Validation; Google Earth Engine*

1. Introduction

Surface soil moisture (SSM), the relative water content of the upper layer of the soil (Adab et al. 2020), is an important parameter that influences the interactions of the earth-atmosphere system (Srivastava et al. 2013; Vogel et al. 2017). SSM plays a key role in Earth's natural processes regulating global biogeochemical cycles and the global energy balance (Carlson et al. 2019; Bao et al. 2018; Deng et al. 2019a). Given the importance of SSM, knowledge of its dynamics is essential for understanding a variety of environmental and socio-economic processes. Such insights can be useful for sustainable water resource management, early warning of natural hazards such as floods and droughts, monitoring natural ecosystems (Choi et al. 2012; Piles et al. 2016; Deng et al. 2019a) and the impact assessment on vegetation vitality (Shi et al. 2014; Fuzzo et al. 2019). It is also applicable to a variety of hydrological (Suman et al. 2020) and weather forecasting models (Panegrossi et al. 2011) at both regional and global scales. Moreover, the study of SSM at the national wide level can be exploited as a decision-making tool (Deng et al. 2019b). Accurate information on SSM can help farmers in crop

yield by making better management in irrigation practices, especially in arid and semi-arid regions (Adeyemi et al. 2017). Thus, it is possible to address food and water security challenges that are at risk due to climate change at a global level. Today, proper irrigation management is crucial as most of the water is consumed for irrigation.

Traditionally, soil moisture measurement can be carried out by ground instrumentation (Petropoulos et al. 2013). There are many advantages of in-situ instruments for measuring soil moisture distribution. These include easy installation, maintenance and operation, instrument portability, the possibility of measuring at different depths and relatively direct measurement. Today, soil moisture distribution is considered quite challenging in large-scale areas using traditional methods because of the heterogeneity of landscapes (Gruber et al. 2020). The large spatial and temporal variability of SSM can explain this challenge as soil moisture depends on parameters which are likely to vary spatially such as soil structure, precipitation, land cover and topography (Bao et al. 2018; Gupta et al. 2021). As a result, for large-scale areas, point measurement of soil moisture is not useful as the installation of ground networks is quite time-consuming and costly (Liu et al. 2022). However, at local scale there are some SSM observation networks that have a database of point measurements, such as the International Soil Moisture Network (ISMN) (Dorigo et al. 2021).

In the recent decades, there has been rapid technological development in the domain of Earth Observation (EO). A number of techniques has been developed to estimate SSM over areas of large and diverse geographic scales (Petropoulos et al. 2018a). The techniques used to retrieve SSM involve optical, thermal and microwave satellite sensors (Petropoulos et al. 2015a). Optical and thermal sensors operate in visible/infrared parts of the electromagnetic radiation spectrum (EMR). Microwave sensors included two main categories, active and passive, are promising because of their direct data acquisition, day, and night due to satellites' revisit period and their low sensitivity to cloud and atmospheric conditions. As for the operation of active sensors, they have better spatial resolution than passive sensors. However, vegetation cover, surface roughness and topography are some of the factors that affect the retrieval of SSM from active sensors (Li et al. 2021). In contrast, passive sensors have higher accuracy in SSM retrievals due to higher temporal resolution and thus are more suitable for SSM monitoring.

The use of EO technology in SSM retrievals has reached a very satisfactory level of maturity, as evidenced and by the large number of relevant operational products currently available (e.g. see review by Petropoulos et al. 2018b). Those products are derived from spaceborne systems such as the Advanced Scatterometer with MetOp-A and MetOp-B (C-band scatterometer), the Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer2 (AMSR-2) (Bindlish et al., 2018), Windsat/Cariolos (Li et al. 2010) and the FengYun-3C (FY-3C) (Zhang et al. 2020). Two of the most important missions for space based SSM retrievals are the European Space Agency's (ESA) Soil Moisture and Ocean Salinity (SMOS) mission, and NASA's Soil Moisture Active and Passive (SMAP) mission (Kerr et al. 2012; Petropoulos et al. 2014; Colliander et al. 2021).

Given the large number of satellite operational SM product, it is quite important to carry out studies on the accuracy of the operational products as it achieves data reliability control and improves

operational retrieval algorithms (Gruber et al. 2020). In parallel, with the increased volume of the existing operational SSM products new challenges have been emerged in the context of accessing and processing those datasets. Cloud-based platforms such as the Google Earth Engine (GEE) can help to manage, process, and visualise satellite data more efficiently reducing the volume of data for the user's convenience (Sazib et al. 2018; Greifeneder et al. 2021). SSM datasets can be efficiently processed in terms of cost and time by utilising cloud computing platforms creating new applications and opportunities for their use.

Several studies have been conducted to evaluate the accuracy of those operational SSM products in different places worldwide with SMAP SM datasets attracting a large of portion of them. Yet, notably studies focusing specifically on soil moisture retrieval from the SMAP satellite are scarce for arid/semi-arid regions such as in the Mediterranean environment. For example, Suman et al. (2020) investigated the performance of the SMAP L4 SM product at selected experimental sites for four different continents. The authors reported a high performance of the SMAP product for all the experimental sites included in their study. In another study, Gupta et al. (2021) followed a different way of estimating soil moisture by incorporating soil temperature (ST) using SMAP data for different seasonal periods. In their work, accuracy of the product was obtained by applying linear regression model. At a second time, multiple linear regression was also applied using soil temperature as a third variable to achieve the best accuracy of SM retrieval. A more recent study involving the Tibetan Plateau examined the SMAP L3_36km and the 9km product compared to ground data from the Naqu observation network (Deng et al. 2022). The accuracy of those products was equally high with the only difference being that in this study the results are highly dependent on the presence of precipitation which is common in the area and affects the variability of the SSM.

In light of the above, in the current study the GEE Python Application Programming Interface is utilised to evaluate the SMAP 9 km product across various sites in Central Greece, representing a typical Mediterranean semi-arid environment. To achieve this goal, co-orbital ground measurements are used together with the SMAP satellite data from year 2020. As part of the agreement examination, the influence of factors that affect the agreement between the compared datasets are examined.

2. Experimental setup

2.1. Study area and In-situ measurements

The study area is in Eastern Central Greece, in the prefecture of Boeotia and specifically 110km northwest of Athens. The current plain has a total area of 215 km² and was created by the drainage of Lake Kopaida at the end of the 19th century. The geomorphology of the Kopaida basin has been shaped by the process of karstification, that is, the dissolving action of water on the readily soluble limestone rocks of the area. It is characterised by a flat terrain interrupted by several hills located on the margins of the plain. The area where it is located today is the end of the Boeotian Kifissos River and is a highly arable area with the main crops being cultivated there are wheat, cotton, industrial tomatoes, maize, pulses, and vegetables.

In the present study, an observation network of stations established by Neupublic (<https://www.neupublic.gr/>) in Greece was used for the selection of experimental sites. This network includes field measurements of soil moisture and temperature taken by the Drill and Drop (DnD) instrument at a depth of 5 cm. For the selection of experimental sites, specific criteria based on other studies (Deng et al. 2019a; Gupta et al. 2021) were considered. These criteria are diversity of crop types, homogeneity of stations within 1 km radius to provide diversity in the study area, large distance of one station from another so that no two stations are in the same pixel and the reliability of results is greater, dispersion of sites throughout the study area. The area consists of 5 monitoring stations under two different annual crop types. The geographical location of the selected sites is shown in **Figure 1**. A summary of the validation sites is described in **Table 1**, where the first column shows the ID of each station, while the second column shows the crop type for each station. The third and fourth columns show the planting and harvesting dates for each crop.

Table 1. A description of Neupublic’s SSM monitoring stations utilized in this study area.

Point ID	Crop type	Start Date	End Date
Kopaida 11	Cotton	19/06/2020	10/09/2020
Kopaida 12	Cotton	19/06/2020	10/09/2020
Kopaida 21	Cotton	19/06/2020	10/09/2020
Kopaida 28	Tomato	18/06/2020	31/08/2020
Kopaida 29	Tomato	18/06/2020	31/08/2020

Figure 1. The geographical location of the study area and the footprint of the SMAP pixels. Red dots represent cotton crops, while the black triangle symbol represents tomato crops

2.2. SMAP Level 3 SM product (9km)

The SMAP mission was launched in January 2015 having initial a ~36km spatial, that was latter reduced to 9km, and 2-3 days temporal resolution (Chan et al. 2018). The SMAP mission has the capability to measure liquid water in the top layer of the soil and can also measure the amount of water between rock materials, organic particles, and minerals if the soil is not covered by water or ice. In this study, the SMAP Level 3 (SPL3SMAP) product was used to retrieve soil moisture estimates using GEE Python API. The SMAP Level 3 (L3) soil moisture product is retrieved from the NSIDC (National Snow and Ice Data Center) (<https://nsidc.org/data/spl3smap/versions/3>). This product has horizontal (H) and vertical (V) brightness temperatures observed at an incidence angle θ 40° (O'Neill et al. 2020). The instrument used is an L-band radiometer of the SMAP active passive system that is designed to measure daily the amount of water in the surface soil on Earth representing the topsoil layer of 0–5 cm. SMAP Level 3 product provides brightness temperature gridded data in both ascending (06:00 p.m. local time) and descending (06:00 a.m. local time) orbits. Together with the SSM predictions are also provided quality assessment flags (O'Neill et al. 2020).

3. Methodology

3.1. Data Pre-processing

In SSM validation studies, several pre-processing steps need to be performed on the different datasets prior to direct comparison between the different datasets. These pre-processing steps include filtering of both the spaceborne, and reference datasets based on data quality flags, rescaling of both datasets to the same units, and temporal matching of the datasets. The same principles were therefore applied to our study.

Only the SMAP SSM Soil Moisture product was used to filter the data based on the quality flags of the datasets used. The version of the ground truth datasets used did not have a quality flag. In our case, based on Ayres et al. (2021) and Li et al. (2022), filtering rules are provided by «retrieval_qual_flag_am/pm», where the flag equals "0", the measurement was accepted while when it equals with "1", the measurement was discarded.

Following the implementation of the data quality flags, the in-situ data were rescaled to the same units ($m^3 m^{-3}$) as the SMAP data by a multiplication of 0.01. Finally, the two datasets were time-matched to produce two separate datasets for the 0600- and 1800-hour measurements. The measured soil moisture values were then correlated with the corresponding values from the satellite measurements based on the satellite orbit and retrieval time.

3.2. Statistical Assessment

For each collocated data set of in-situ and satellite data, descriptive statistics were measured for a more accurate distribution of the data. A series of statistical metrics are used to explore the agreement between ground measurements and the SMAP satellite retrievals based on Global Validation Protocol (Gruber et al. 2020). These statistical metrics are Sample Size (N), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), correlation coefficient (R), bias (MBE), scatter (MSD), Root Mean Square Difference (RMSD), Unbiased Root Mean Square Difference (ubRMSD) and Slope and Intercept of the Major

Axis Regression linear fit. Their mathematical equations are described in **Table 2**. Further details on each metric are described in [Silk \(1979\)](#), [Willmoot \(1981\)](#), [Burt et al. \(1996\)](#) and [Legates et al. \(1999\)](#). Statistical metrics previously utilised in published studies are used to calculate the comparisons between predicted and measured measurements. ([Entekhabi et al. 2010](#); [Petropoulos et al. 2015b](#); [Suman et al. 2020](#); [Gupta et al. 2021](#); [Deng et al. 2022](#)).

Table 2. Statistical metrics used in evaluating the accuracy between ground measurements and retrieved SMAP satellite data. "N" represents the in-situ observations, "P" represents the "predicted" values, and "O" represents the "observed" values. Subscripts $i=1$. The horizontal line represents the mean value.

Name	Description	Mathematical Equation
MAE	Mean Absolute Error	$MAE = N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N P_i - O_i ^2$
R	Correlation coefficient	$R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - \bar{P})(O_i - \bar{O})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^N (O_i - \bar{O})^2 (P_i - \bar{P})^2}}$
Bias/MBE	Bias (or Mean Bias Error)	$bias = MBE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i - O_i)$
RMSD	Root Mean Square Difference	$RMSD = \sqrt{bias^2 + scatter^2}$
ubRMSD	Unbiased Root Mean Square Difference	$ubRMSD = \sqrt{RMSD^2 - bias^2}$

4. Results

The SMAP L3 data were compared with the corresponding field measurements to evaluate the assessment of the SMAP satellite product. In the presented results, the performance of the model across different datasets and time points is evaluated using various metrics. The main results are presented in **Table 3** and **Figure 2**. For each site, a relatively good agreement between the two data sets is identified during both ascending and descending time for all days of comparison. This is evidenced by the RMSD value which ranges for the ascending orbit (06.00am) between 0.126 - 0.221 $m^3 m^{-3}$ and for the descending orbit 18.00pm between 0.120 - 0.216 $m^3 m^{-3}$. The highest accuracy is found in the cotton crop for both the morning (MAE = 0.102 $m^3 m^{-3}$, R = 0.305, MBE = -0.092 $m^3 m^{-3}$, RMSD = 0.126 $m^3 m^{-3}$, ubRMSE = 0.087 $m^3 m^{-3}$) and for the afternoon satellite passtime (MAE = 0.088 $m^3 m^{-3}$, R = -0.115, MBE = -0.057 $m^3 m^{-3}$, RMSD = 0.120 $m^3 m^{-3}$, ubRMSD = 0.106 $m^3 m^{-3}$). At the same time, in both analyses, low agreement is obtained for the tomato crop RMSD = 0.221/0.216 $m^3 m^{-3}$, respectively. In overall analysis, a slight underestimation of the satellite data by the field data is observed.

Table 3. Results of comparison between SMAP L3 SM and ground data both ascending and descending orbit

Time	Dataset	N	MAE	R	Bias	RMSD	ubRMSD	Slope	Intercept
0600 am	kopaida 11	38	0.160	0.467	-0.046	0.179	0.173	0.132	0.151
	kopaida 12	38	0.102	0.305	-0.092	0.126	0.087	0.174	0.139
	kopaida 21	38	0.101	-0.237	-0.06	0.136	0.122	-0.11	0.208
	kopaida 28	33	0.125	0.204	-0.099	0.155	0.119	0.094	0.163
	kopaida 29	33	0.211	-0.017	-0.21	0.221	0.068	-0.022	0.203
1800 pm	kopaida 11	39	0.170	0.235	-0.042	0.192	0.188	0.057	0.182
	kopaida 12	37	0.106	0.202	-0.091	0.129	0.091	0.088	0.164
	kopaida 21	38	0.088	-0.115	-0.057	0.12	0.106	-0.030	0.183
	kopaida 28	31	0.110	0.250	-0.083	0.137	0.109	0.100	0.166
	kopaida 29	30	0.209	0.037	-0.209	0.216	0.053	0.030	0.179

Figure 2. Agreement between SMAP L3 SM and ground data based on satellite orbit

The noticeable agreement between the two datasets during the ascending orbit at 06:00 AM and descending orbit at 18:00 PM is worth mentioning with the main results being presented in **Table 4** and **Figure 3**. This is supported by the RMSD values, which range from 0.126 to 0.221 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ and 0.120 to 0.216 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, respectively for each crop type. The analysis confirms a solid correlation between soil moisture estimates obtained from both satellite and field measurements. Notably, the cotton crop displays the highest precision, particularly in the morning (MAE = 0.102 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, R = 0.305, MBE = -0.092 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, RMSD = 0.126 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, and ubRMSD = 0.087 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$). Simultaneously, during the afternoon satellite transit period, the cotton harvest demonstrated exceptional precision (MAE = 0.088 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, R = -0.115, MBE = -0.057 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, RMSD = 0.120 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$, and ubRMSD = 0.106 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$). Conversely, both studies highlight reduced accuracy for the tomato crop, denoted by increased RMSD (0.221 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$ and 0.216 $\text{m}^3 \text{m}^{-3}$) during the morning and afternoon orbits correspondingly.

Table 4. Agreement between SMAP L3 SM and ground data both ascending and descending orbit

	MAE	R	Bias	RMSE	ubRMSE	Slope	Intercept
Tomato (PM)	0.125	0.158	-0.106	0.152	0.152	0.054	0.171
Cotton (PM)	0.170	0.235	-0.042	0.192	0.192	0.057	0.182
Cotton (AM)	0.160	0.467	-0.046	0.179	0.179	0.132	0.151
Tomato (AM)	0.133	0.104	-0.112	0.162	0.162	0.049	0.173

Figure 3. SMAP L3 SSM agreement for both the am (left) and pm (right) overpasses for both the tomato and cotton fields

5. Discussion

The present's study main objective was to evaluate the soil moisture product SMAP L3 SM using ground data from a network of sites in Kopaida, a typical Mediterranean environment for the summer of 2020. This is an area with intensive agricultural activity and increased water needs due to the crops it produces. Overall, the study gave a reasonable agreement of the product, with the cotton crop showing the best accuracy. However, in all analysis, it is observed that an underestimation of the satellite data by the ground data. However, there are stations where the product showed a low performance. This is likely to be due to a variety of reasons.

One of them is errors caused by the measurement accuracy of the sensors. While the ground truth data are quite useful for estimating satellite products, they are characterised by errors due to problems in the way they are represented and their instrumentation. These problems can be the way and depth of instrument installation, the method of measurement, calibration techniques, lack of instrument maintenance (Dorigo et al. 2013). The validation of satellite products may depend largely on these errors. Regarding the penetration depth of the instrument, this differs from the field data. Specifically, the L-band of the SMAP has a depth of 3 to 7 cm and it varies based on SSM (Owe et al. 2008) while the in-situ sensors are placed at a depth of about 5 cm. This means that the in-situ

instrumentation is deeper than the L-band (Wang et al. 2021). This reason is likely to account for the bias observed in the results (**Table 3 and 4**).

A possible reason for the underestimation of satellite data compared to ground data and at the same time the dry bias is that it is mainly observed during the summer months as has been shown in other studies (Kang et al. 2016; Oozeer et al. 2020). However, it is not clearly demonstrated by the scientific community that there is a systematic underestimation or overestimation of soil moisture data.

The sample size and spatial distribution of measurements may also explain the low accuracy performance at specific stations (Table 3). This is since these crops are classified as annual crops and thus only one growing season is investigated over a three-month period (June - September). The agreement improvement of the satellite product could be achieved by improving point measurements with techniques such as the use of dense networks (Srivastava et al. 2017).

In addition, factors such as topographic complexity and vegetation density play a crucial role in the accuracy of product retrieval (Zhang et al. 2017; El Hajj et al. 2018). The type of land use significantly determines the rate of agreement. In this case, cotton gives higher accuracy than tomato because the microwave signal of the L-band penetrates more easily compared to the canopy of tomato. Thus, RMSD shows a low value, and the R is better compared to the tomato crop. The water content of the vegetation has an equally important role in the accuracy of product recovery as it is affected by microwave radiation. Also, microwave signatures are affected by topographical features (Engman et al. 1995). However, it should be noted that measurements in the morning hours were slightly better compared to the afternoon hours. Studies show that in the summer months and during the daytime the canopy layer is more visible compared to the nighttime (Chen et al. 2013).

In summary, the study shows that the performance of the product can be influenced by a variety of factors such as the in-situ instrumentation, the depth of penetration of satellite and in-situ data and the type of land cover highlighting the water content of the vegetation and the phenological changes occurring in them. Thus, the results of the present study have a slightly lower agreement compared to the results of other studies (Suman et al. 2020; Gupta et al. 2021; Deng et al. 2022).

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the comparative assessment of SMAP Level 3 data with field measurements offers valuable insights into the performance and limitations of the satellite product in estimating soil moisture content across agricultural landscapes. The observed congruence between satellite and field data, especially in cotton crops, underscores the reliability of the SMAP satellite product. However, the crop-specific variations highlight the importance of tailoring satellite-based estimations to the unique characteristics of different crops.

The identified underestimation of satellite data relative to field measurements suggests a need for further refinement in calibration or correction methodologies to enhance accuracy. Addressing these

inherent biases is crucial for ensuring the reliability of satellite-derived soil moisture estimates in practical applications, such as precision agriculture and water resource management.

Moving forward, future research should focus on refining satellite algorithms to account for crop-specific nuances and improve overall accuracy. Additionally, ongoing efforts to validate and calibrate satellite data against ground measurements will contribute to advancing the reliability of environmental monitoring tools. The findings presented herein contribute to the ongoing dialogue on the utilization and enhancement of satellite products, emphasizing the need for nuanced approaches in capturing the complexity of soil moisture dynamics in diverse agricultural settings. Results obtained from this study could yield valuable insights into optimizing irrigation given the high level of agricultural activity in the Kopaida region and the significant importance of water resource management.

References

- Adab, H., Morbidelli, R., Saltalippi, C., Moradian, M., & Ghalhari, G. a. F. (2020). Machine Learning to Estimate Surface Soil Moisture from Remote Sensing Data. *Water*, 12(11), 3223. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w12113223>
- Adeyemi, O., Grove, I. G., Peets, S., & Norton, T. (2017). Advanced monitoring and management systems for improving sustainability in precision irrigation. *Sustainability*, 9(3), 353. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su9030353>
- Ayres, E., Colliander, A., Cosh, M. H., Roberti, J. A., Simkin, S., & Genazzio, M. A. (2021). Validation of SMAP soil moisture at terrestrial National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON) sites show potential for soil moisture retrieval in forested areas. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 14, 10903–10918. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2021.3121206>
- Bao, Y., Lin, L., Wu, S., Deng, K. a. K., & Petropoulos, G. P. (2018). Surface soil moisture retrievals over partially vegetated areas from the synergy of Sentinel-1 and Landsat 8 data using a modified water-cloud model. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 72, 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2018.05.026>
- Bindlish, R., Cosh, M. H., Jackson, T. J., Koike, T., Fujii, H., Chan, S. K., Asanuma, J., Berg, A., Bosch, D. D., Caldwell, T. G., Collins, C. H., McNairn, H., Martínez-Fernández, J., Prueger, J. H., Rowlandson, T., Seyfried, M. S., Starks, P. J., Thibeault, M., Van Der Velde, R., . . . Coopersmith, E. J. (2018). GCOM-W AMSR2 Soil moisture product validation using core Validation sites. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 11(1), 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2017.2754293>
- Burt, J. M., Barber, G. M., & Rigby, D. L. (1996). *Elementary statistics for geographers*. <http://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA06664153>
- Carlson, T. N., & Petropoulos, G. P. (2019). A new method for estimating of evapotranspiration and surface soil moisture from optical and thermal infrared measurements: the simplified triangle. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 40(20), 7716–7729. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2019.1601288>

- Chan, S., Bindlish, R., O'Neill, P. E., Jackson, T. J., Njoku, E. G., Dunbar, S., Chaubell, J., Piepmeier, J., Yueh, S., Entekhabi, D., Colliander, A., Chen, F., Cosh, M. H., Caldwell, T. G., Walker, J. P., Berg, A., McNairn, H., Thibeault, M., Martínez-Fernández, J., . . . Kerr, Y. H. (2018). Development and assessment of the SMAP enhanced passive soil moisture product. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 204, 931–941. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.08.025>
- Chen, Y.; Yang, K.; Qin, J.; Zhao, L.; Tang, W.; Han, M. Evaluation of AMSR-E retrievals and GLDAS simulations against observations of a soil moisture network on the central tibetan plateau. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.* 2013, 118, 4466–4475.
- Choi, M., & Hur, Y. (2012). A microwave-optical/infrared disaggregation for improving spatial representation of soil moisture using AMSR-E and MODIS products. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 124, 259–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2012.05.009>
- Colliander, A., Reichle, R. H., Crow, W. T., Cosh, M. H., Chen, F., Chan, S., Das, N. N., Bindlish, R., Chaubell, J., Kim, S., Liu, Q., O'Neill, P., Dunbar, S., Dang, L., Kimball, J. S., Jackson, T. J., Jassar, H. K. A., Asanuma, J., Bhattacharya, B. K., . . . Yueh, S. (2021). Validation of Soil Moisture Data Products From the NASA SMAP Mission. *IEEE Journal of Selected Topics in Applied Earth Observations and Remote Sensing*, 15, 364–392. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jstars.2021.3124743>
- Deng, K. a. K., Lamine, S., Pavlides, A., Petropoulos, G. P., Bao, Y., Srivastava, P. K., & Guan, Y. (2019a). Large scale operational soil moisture mapping from passive MW radiometry: SMOS product evaluation in Europe & USA. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 80, 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2019.04.015>
- Deng, K. a. K., Lamine, S., Pavlides, A., Petropoulos, G. P., Srivastava, P. K., Bao, Y., Hristopulos, D. T., & Anagnostopoulos, V. (2019b). Operational Soil Moisture from ASCAT in Support of Water Resources Management. *Remote Sensing*, 11(5), 579. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs11050579>
- Deng, K. a. K., Petropoulos, G. P., Bao, Y., Pavlides, A., Chaibou, A. a. S., & Habtemicheal, B. A. (2022). An examination of the SMAP operational soil moisture products accuracy at the Tibetan Plateau. *Remote Sensing*, 14(24), 6255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14246255>
- Dorigo, W., Himmelbauer, I., Aberer, D., Schremmer, L., Petrakovic, I., Zappa, L., Preimesberger, W., Xaver, A., Annor, F. O., Ardö, J., Baldocchi, D. D., Bitelli, M., Blöschl, G., Bogena, H., Brocca, L., Calvet, J., Camarero, J. J., Capello, G., Choi, M., . . . Sabia, R. (2021). The International Soil Moisture Network: serving Earth system science for over a decade. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 25(11), 5749–5804. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-25-5749-2021>
- Dorigo, W.A., Xaver, A., Vreugdenhil, M., Gruber, A., Hegyiová, A., Sanchis-Dufau, A.D., Zamojski, D., et al. (2013). Global automated quality control of in situ soil moisture data from the international soil moisture network. *Vadose Zone J.* 12 (3), 0. <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2012.0097>
- Engman, E.T.; Chauhan, N. Status of microwave soil moisture measurements with remote sensing. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 1995, 51, 189–198
- El Hajj, M.; Baghdadi, N.; Zribi, M.; Rodríguez-Fernández, N.; Wigneron, J.P.; Al-Yaari, A.; Al Bitar, A.; Albergel, C.; Calvet, J.-C. Evaluation of SMOS, SMAP, ASCAT and Sentinel-1 soil moisture products at sites in southwestern France. *Remote Sens.* 2018, 10, 569

- Entekhabi, D., Njoku, E. G., O'Neill, P. E., Kellogg, K., Crow, W. T., Edelstein, W., Entin, J., Goodman, S. E., Jackson, T. J., Johnson, J. T., Kimball, J. S., Piepmeier, J. R., Koster, R. D., Martin, M. A., McDonald, K. C., Moghaddam, M., Moran, S., Reichle, R. H., Shi, J., . . . Van Zyl, J. (2010). The Soil Moisture Active Passive (SMAP) mission. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, 98(5), 704–716. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jproc.2010.2043918>
- Fuzzo, D. F. S., Carlson, T. N., Kourgialas, N. N., & Petropoulos, G. P. (2019). Coupling remote sensing with a water balance model for soybean yield predictions over large areas. *Earth Science Informatics*, 13(2), 345–359. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-019-00424-w>
- Greifeneder, F., Notarnicola, C., & Wagner, W. (2021). A Machine Learning-Based Approach for Surface Soil Moisture Estimations with Google Earth Engine. *Remote Sensing*, 13(11), 2099. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13112099>
- Gruber, A., Paloscia, S., Santi, E., Notarnicola, C., Pasolli, L., Smolander, T., Pulliainen, J., Mittelbach, H., Dorigo, W., & Wagner, W. (2014). Performance inter-comparison of soil moisture retrieval models for the MetOp-A ASCAT instrument. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium*. <https://doi.org/10.1109/igarss.2014.6946969>
- Gruber, A. D., De Lannoy, G., Albergel, C., Al-Yaari, A., Brocca, L., Calvet, J., Colliander, A., Cosh, M. H., Crow, W. T., Dorigo, W., Draper, C. S., Hirschi, M., Kerr, Y., Konings, A. G., Lahoz, W., McColl, K. A., Montzka, C., Muñoz-Sabater, J., Peng, J., . . . Wagner, W. (2020). Validation practices for satellite soil moisture retrievals: What are (the) errors? *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 244, 111806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111806>
- Gupta, D., Srivastava, P., Singh, A., Petropoulos, G., Stathopoulos, N., Prasad, R. (2021). SMAP Soil Moisture Product Assessment over Wales, UK. Using Observations from the WSMN Ground Monitoring Network. *Sustainability* 2021, 13 (11), 6019. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13116019>
- Kang, C. S., Kanniah, K. D., Kerr, Y., & Varotsos, C. A. (2016). Analysis of in-situ soil moisture data and validation of SMOS soil moisture products at selected agricultural sites over a tropical region. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 37(16), 3636–3654. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2016.1201229>
- Kerr, Y. H., Waldteufel, P., Richaume, P., Wigneron, J., Ferrazzoli, P., Mahmoodi, A., Bitar, A. A., Cabot, F., Gruhier, C., Juglea, S. E., Leroux, D., Mialon, A., & Delwart, S. (2012). The SMOS soil moisture Retrieval Algorithm. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*, 50(5), 1384–1403. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tgrs.2012.2184548>
- Legates, D. R., & McCabe, G. J. (1999). Evaluating the use of “goodness-of-fit” Measures in hydrologic and hydroclimatic model validation. *Water Resources Research*, 35(1), 233–241. <https://doi.org/10.1029/1998wr900018>
- Li, X., Wigneron, J.-P., Fan, L., Frappart, F., Yueh, S.-H., Colliander A., Ebtehaj, A., Gao, L., Fernandez-Moran, R., Liu, X., Wang, M., Ma, H., Moisy, C. & Ciais, P. (2022). A new SMAP soil moisture and vegetation optical depth product (SMAP-IB): Algorithm, assessment and inter-comparison. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 271, 112921. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2022.112921>
- Li, Z., Leng, P., Zhou, C., Chen, K., Zhou, F., & Shang, G. (2021). Soil moisture retrieval from remote sensing measurements: Current knowledge and directions for the future. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 218, 103673. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103673>

- Liu, Y., & Yang, Y. (2022). Advances in the Quality of Global soil Moisture Products: A review. *Remote Sensing*, 14(15), 3741. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14153741>
- O'Neill, P.E., Chan, S., Njoku, E.G., Jackson, T., Bindlish, R., Chaubell, J., 2020. SMAP L3 Radiometer Global Daily 36 km EASE-Grid Soil Moisture, Version 7. NASA National Snow and Ice Data Center Distributed Active Archive Center, Boulder, Colorado USA. <https://doi.org/10.5067/HH4SZ2PXSP6A>
- Oozeer, M. Y., Fletcher, C. D., & Champagne, C. M. (2020). Evaluation of Satellite-Derived Surface Soil Moisture Products over Agricultural Regions of Canada. *Remote Sensing*, 12(9), 1455. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12091455>
- Panegrossi, G., Ferretti, R., Pulvirenti, L., & Pierdicca, N. (2011). Impact of ASAR soil moisture data on the MM5 precipitation forecast for the Tanaro flood event of April 2009. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 11(12), 3135–3149. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-11-3135-2011>
- Petropoulos, G. P. (2013). *Remote sensing of energy fluxes and soil moisture content*. CRC Press.
- Petropoulos, G. P., Ireland, G., & Barrett, B. (2015a). Surface soil moisture retrievals from remote sensing: Current status, products & future trends. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts a/B/C*, 83–84, 36–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2015.02.009>
- Petropoulos, G. P., Ireland, G., & Srivastava, P. K. (2015b). Evaluation of the soil moisture Operational Estimates from SMOS in Europe: Results over diverse ecosystems. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 15(9), 5243–5251. <https://doi.org/10.1109/jsen.2015.2427657>
- Petropoulos, G. P., Ireland, G., Srivastava, P. K., & Ioannou-Katidis, P. (2014). An appraisal of the accuracy of operational soil moisture estimates from SMOS MIRAS using validated in situ observations acquired in a Mediterranean environment. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 35(13), 5239–5250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2150704x.2014.933277>
- Petropoulos, G. P., Srivastava, P. K., Ferentinos, K. P., & Hristopoulos, D. (2018a). Evaluating the capabilities of optical/TIR imaging sensing systems for quantifying soil water content. *Geocarto International*, 35(5), 494–511. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2018.1520926>
- Petropoulos, G. P., Srivastava, P. K., Piles, M., & Pearson, S. (2018b). Earth Observation-Based operational estimation of soil moisture and evapotranspiration for agricultural crops in support of sustainable water management. *Sustainability*, 10(2), 181. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10010181>
- Piles, M., Petropoulos, G. P., Sánchez, N., González-Zamora, Á., & Ireland, G. (2016). Towards improved spatio-temporal resolution soil moisture retrievals from the synergy of SMOS and MSG SEVIRI spaceborne observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 180, 403–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2016.02.048>
- Sazib, N., Mladenova, I. E., & Bolten, J. D. (2018). Leveraging the Google Earth engine for drought assessment using global soil moisture data. *Remote Sensing*, 10(8), 1265. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs10081265>
- Shi, Q., & Liang, S. (2014). Surface-sensible and latent heat fluxes over the Tibetan Plateau from ground measurements, reanalysis, and satellite data. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 14(11), 5659–5677. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-14-5659-2014>

- Silk, J. (1979). *Statistical concepts in Geography*. Allen & Unwin Australia.
- Srivastava, P. K., Han, D., Rico-Ramirez, M. A., Al-Shrafany, D., & Islam, T. (2013). Data fusion techniques for improving soil moisture deficit using SMOS satellite and WRF-NOAH land Surface model. *Water Resources Management*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11269-013-0452-7>
- Srivastava, P.K. Satellite soil moisture: Review of theory and applications in water resources. *Water Resour. Manag.* 2017, 31, 3161–3176.
- Suman, S., Srivastava, P. K., Petropoulos, G. P., Pandey, D. K., & O'Neill, P. (2020). Appraisal of SMAP Operational Soil Moisture Product from a Global Perspective. *Remote Sensing*, 12(12), 1977. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12121977>
- Vogel, M. M., Orth, R., Chéruy, F., Hagemann, S., Lorenz, R., Van Den Hurk, B., & Seneviratne, S. I. (2017). Regional amplification of projected changes in extreme temperatures strongly controlled by soil moisture-temperature feedbacks. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 44(3), 1511–1519. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016gl071235>
- Wang, X., Lü, H., Crow, W. T., Zhu, Y., Wang, Q., Su, J., Zheng, J., & Gou, Q. (2021). Assessment of SMOS and SMAP soil moisture products against new estimates combining physical model, a statistical model, and in-situ observations: A case study over the Huai River Basin, China. *Journal of Hydrology*, 598, 126468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2021.126468>
- Willmott, C. J. (1981). ON THE VALIDATION OF MODELS. *Physical Geography*, 2(2), 184–194. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02723646.1981.10642213>
- Zhang, C.; Cheng, Q.; Yang, J.; Zhao, J.; Cui, T.J. Broadband metamaterial for optical transparency and microwave absorption. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 2017, 110, 143511.
- Zhang, S., Weng, F., & Yao, W. (2020). A Multivariable Approach for Estimating Soil Moisture from Microwave Radiation Imager (MWRI). *Journal of Meteorological Research*, 34(4), 732–747. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13351-020-9203-x>